

Seasonal Economic Fluctuations Drive Illegal Resource Extraction

Abstract

The illegal extraction of natural resources undermines progress toward environmental and development goals at all scales. In rural economies, the social determinants of crime, such as income, vary with predictable seasonal climate patterns, potentially enabling targeted interventions. Here, we combine 13 years of forestry patrol arrest records from Pemba (Zanzibar), Tanzania, with biweekly household economic and weather data to trace how weather fluctuations propagate through the local economy, reliably influencing illegal forestry activity. Our results show that seasonal income cycles directly influence the amount of illegal forestry, causing an approximately 20% cyclical change throughout the year. Illegal resource extraction peaks during periods of low income, which are heavily influenced by the seasonal cycles of the clove and fishing industries, and downstream manufacturing and retail sectors. We then use climate-change projections for the island to simulate how shifts in the ‘short rains’ season alter rates of illegal resource extraction. These results suggest that to curb illegal resource extraction in seasonal economies, policy initiatives should prioritize income-smoothing measures during predictable low-income periods. We hope that our adaptable analytical framework offers a powerful tool for identifying leverage points to mitigate illegal activities and advance sustainable resource governance.

Keywords— Seasonality, Natural Resources, Conservation, Illegal Resource Use

Introduction

Changes in economic conditions lead individuals to adapt their livelihood strategies by reallocating effort to other sources of income. When formal income opportunities contract, people turn to any available source of earnings—even those that violate local norms, regulations, or laws [1, 2]. In resource-dependent economies, adaptive responses to low income frequently take the form of illegal resource extraction, which provides short-term relief at the cost of potentially accelerating the degradation of the very resources on which livelihoods depend, potentially amplifying the long-run impacts of climate change [3].

Research has long linked aggregate economic performance to environmental outcomes: wealthier countries tend to experience lower rates of illegal deforestation and other forms of environmental degradation. This pattern is consistent with an environmental Kuznets-type (i.e., an inverted U-shaped) relationship between economic development and environmental quality [4–6]. Yet such macro-level associations obscure the microeconomic mechanisms that translate income fluctuations into resource use decisions. In low-income settings where households depend directly on natural resources for income and subsistence, short-term variation in earnings can generate liquidity shocks that alter labor allocation, extraction effort, and compliance with environmental regulation [7–9]. A growing body of evidence emphasizes how seasonal or weather-induced income instability drives shifts in illegal or unsustainable activities [10–14]. Nevertheless, rigorous empirical analysis of how intra-annual, particularly seasonal, economic fluctuations influence environmental crime remains scarce, particularly in

43 developing economies where both income and enforcement capacity are highly variable.

44 Among populations directly dependent on local natural resources, increased extraction from
45 nearby lands and seas is a common coping response to income shortfalls and market volatility
46 [15–17]. When households have limited liquidity, they often smooth consumption by reallocating
47 labor toward extractive or informal activities, including land clearing, overharvesting,
48 or the use of prohibited gear and practices [18–20]. Such behavioral responses often reflect
49 the absence of formal insurance and credit markets in rural economies and may result in
50 poverty–environment traps [7, 21].

51 These short-term adaptations can generate long-term ecological and institutional conse-
52 quences. Because many ecological processes are nonlinear, threshold-dependent, and season-
53 ally dynamic, even marginal increases in extraction pressure or shifts in timing can trigger
54 disproportionate declines in stock resilience and ecosystem stability [22–24]. These dynamics,
55 in turn, can undermine local management institutions and amplify feedback loops between
56 economic distress and environmental degradation. However, these local-level processes are
57 often invisible in annual, aggregate statistics [23, 25].

58 In resource-dependent economies, seasonality remains one of the most fundamental drivers
59 of income volatility and livelihood risk [26–28]. Fluctuations in rainfall, harvests, and market
60 activity shape not only consumption and labor allocation but also compliance with environ-
61 mental regulations and pressure on local commons. With climate change expected to inten-
62 sify seasonal extremes and rainfall variability across much of the developing world [29–32],
63 the interaction between seasonal economic cycles and environmentally destructive behavior
64 has become increasingly salient for both economic and ecological research. The sectors most
65 exposed—agriculture (including animal husbandry), fishing, and forestry—are precisely those
66 where short-term shocks in earnings can spill over into illegal or unsustainable extraction
67 [33–36]. These patterns matter far beyond local contexts: roughly one quarter of the world’s
68 population, and up to two-thirds of the rural population in tropical countries, depend directly
69 on natural resource–based livelihoods for food and income [37–40].

70 Understanding how seasonal economic conditions translate into illegal resource extraction is,
71 therefore, central to designing effective conservation and governance strategies. Yet empirical
72 progress has been limited by data constraints. Fine-grained information on illegal environ-
73 mental activities is notoriously scarce: they are rarely captured in administrative statistics
74 or media reports, and direct observation is often infeasible. Likewise, even for legal economic
75 activities, socioeconomic data at sub-annual resolution remain extremely limited in most
76 low-income settings. While advances in remote sensing and high-frequency environmental
77 monitoring now allow researchers to observe the biophysical rhythms of ecosystems with re-
78 markable precision, linking these to the economic behaviors that drive ecological degradation
79 continues to pose one of the central empirical challenges in development and environmental
80 economics.

81 In this paper, we develop a set of analytic and generative models to examine how seasonality
82 mechanistically influences illegal resource extraction through sector-specific economic effects.
83 We use these frameworks to build and validate statistical models that estimate (i) the im-
84 pact of climate on seasonal economic performance and (ii) the impact of seasonal economic
85 performance on illegal forestry activity. Our analysis draws on a uniquely high-resolution
86 dataset comprising more than four years of bi-weekly journals documenting economic pro-
87 duction across over 300 households in Pemba, Tanzania, as well as daily government arrest
88 records of illegal timber harvesting. With these data, we measure the degree of illegal resource
89 extraction that is a predictable consequence of seasonal fluctuations in earnings, particularly

90 from sectors that generate cash income. Overall, our analysis highlights the importance of
91 intersectoral linkages and temporal economic rhythms in shaping environmental outcomes, un-
92 derscoring the need for conservation and climate adaptation policies that account for seasonal
93 economic dynamics.

94 **Results**

95 Over the 15-year observation period, we recorded a total of 745 cases of illegal timber ex-
96 traction on Pemba, with 72% involving cutting without permits, and the other 28% involving
97 transport without permits. This averages 46 cases per year, or just under one case each week.
98 This corresponds to approximately 8 cases per 100,000 people in Pemba each year. Between
99 2022 and 2026, average household earnings (including the estimated value of subsistence pro-
100 duction) amounted to US\$99.50 [interquartile range = 28.04] per two-week period, equivalent
101 to roughly US\$2,574 per year. This translates to approximately US\$1,287 per year for every
102 working-age adult.

103 **Aggregate Impacts**

104 Seasonal fluctuations in earnings are strongly correlated with illegal resource extraction in
105 Pemba, Tanzania. Panel A of Figure 1 shows the posterior estimate of the elasticity between
106 household earnings and the expected number of illegal cases. This estimate implies that a
107 doubling of income is associated with an average 45% decline in illegal cases. Given that
108 mean daily household income rises from about US\$ 5.2 in May to US\$ 7.2 in August (a 38%
109 increase), seasonal changes in earnings alone account for roughly 20% of the total variation
110 in illegal cases.

111 However, when assessing the economic impact of seasonal fluctuations, average daily earn-
112 ings obscure much of the underlying variation in the data—namely, monthly earnings can
113 vary substantially across years. In Figure 1B, we plot aggregated average estimated house-
114 hold earnings against the number of recorded cases of illegal forestry ($N = 378$ - the number
115 of 2 week periods since January 2011) over all 13 years. The fitted line shows predicted cases
116 as a function of expected earnings. Sectoral effects are incorporated by marginalizing over
117 sectors, that is, by summing sector-specific earnings so that the figure reflects their combined
118 contribution to total household income. Across two-week periods, aggregated average house-
119 hold earnings range from roughly US\$ 60 per period (pre-harvest) to about US\$ 150 when
120 rice and clove harvests coincide. At these extremes, the model predicts approximately a 78%
121 reduction in illegal cases. It is worth noting that the observed earnings range is dampened by
122 the inclusion of both rural and urban households, as in some rural locations we observe up to
123 a fourfold (400%) difference in earnings between high and low seasons.

Figure 1: A: Posterior Estimate of the Elasticity of Earnings in a two-week period on the amount of observed illegal resource extraction (shaded region shows 95% highest posterior density interval [HPDI]). B: Observed illegal resource extraction vs. average household earnings. Each point represents an observed number of illegal resource extraction reports for two weeks. The green line represents the model's estimated mean number of cases as a function of expected total earnings in each period. The green highlighted area is the 95% HPDI. The dashed red lines show the expected number of cases during the lowest observed average income period (higher line) and the highest observed average income period (lower line). C: Posterior parameter estimates of the elasticity of sectoral earnings on the number of reported cases of illegal resource extraction.

124 Sectoral Impacts

125 The detail provided by our household economic data allow us to isolate the impacts of sector-
 126 specific earnings on illegal resource extraction (Figure 1B). These estimates indicate the direc-
 127 tion and proportional strength of each relationship; however, the absolute magnitude of each
 128 sector's causal effect also depends on the temporal variability of its earnings. For instance, if
 129 earnings in one sector fluctuate more strongly over time than in another, its contribution to
 130 changes in illegal resource extraction will be correspondingly amplified or dampened.

131 We find evidence of a negative correlation between earnings in several sectors and illegal
 132 resource extraction. Specifically, this relationship is observed for manufacturing (small-scale
 133 production and repairs; $\mu = -0.13$, $PI_{.95} = [-0.23, -0.03]$), fishing ($\mu = -0.16$, $PI_{.95} =$
 134 $[-0.27, -0.05]$), trade and transport ($\mu = -0.15$, $PI_{.95} = [-0.25, -0.02]$), cloves ($\mu = -0.10$,
 135 $PI_{.95} = [-0.21, -0.010]$), and other (or general) services ($\mu = -0.19$, $PI_{.95} = [-0.42, -0.1]$).
 136 Notably, while these sectors vary in their relative strength, all sectors show a credible negative
 137 effect of earnings on illegal forestry activity, indicating that lost earnings reliably translate to
 138 increasing instances of illegal resource extraction in our study population.

139 Robustness Checks

140 Clove production is highly volatile. Consequently, to test the robustness of our estimates
 141 for 2011-2021, we substituted the backcasted biweekly predicted clove earnings with official
 142 monthly statistics on clove production and prices. These data are publicly available for all
 143 of Pemba since 2011. We find a modest correlation between our backcasted earnings and
 144 observed clove production (Pearson's $r = 0.38$). While this correlation may appear low, it is
 145 reasonable given the irregular boom-and-bust pattern of clove production. The error mainly
 146 arises because the model captures seasonal peaks (timing) but not the exact magnitude or
 147 the periodic boom/busts, leading it to overpredict harvests in years when busts occur, and
 148 under-predict during booms. To correct for this, we replaced the imputed clove earnings
 149 between 2011 and 2022 with the official government data. This adjustment has little effect on
 150 the results, slightly increasing the elasticity from -0.10 to -0.12 and raising the lower bound
 151 of the 90 percent interval to -0.03 .

Figure 2: (A) Sector-specific percentage change in total earnings from October–December (OND) through June, given simulated deviations in OND rainfall (mm) and accounting for the appropriate lag structure of environmental variables. (B) Predicted change in the aggregate number of cases (e.g., households meeting specified outcome criteria) implied by the posterior elasticity of earnings with respect to rainfall. (C) Overall predicted percentage change in total earnings across all sectors. Shaded ribbons indicate 95% HPDI.

153 To understand how projected climate change may alter the economic conditions that drive
 154 illegal extraction, we develop a counterfactual analysis of future climate scenarios. We focus
 155 on the OND (October–December) precipitation season, which represents the primary climatic
 156 anomaly projected for East Africa under future warming [41, 42]. Climate models consistently
 157 predict intensification of the “short rains,” with OND precipitation expected to rise by roughly
 158 10–30 mm per month by mid-century. These changes are likely to reshape local earnings
 159 cycles by altering agricultural yields, seasonal employment, and the liquidity available to
 160 households during the year’s end. To evaluate how such shifts could influence illegal resource
 161 extraction, we perturb the environmental predictors used in the Gaussian-processes in sectoral
 162 earnings—specifically, the OND rain indices and their associated lags—while holding all other
 163 variables at their posterior means. This approach isolates the effect of changes in OND rainfall
 164 on predicted household earnings and, through the estimated elasticity between earnings and
 165 illegal cases, provides a direct estimate of how future rainfall anomalies could alter the seasonal
 166 intensity of illegal resource extraction in Pemba.

167 When we perturb OND rainfall by 5–15 mm (beyond that, estimates become very uncertain)
 168 and propagate the change only through the environmental inputs of the earnings estimation
 169 for the OND months through January and all the way through June the following year to
 170 account for lagged effects (holding other drivers fixed). Aggregate earnings across these 8
 171 months display a roughly symmetrical response: a modest increase in rainfall (+5 mm) reduces
 172 total earnings by $\sim 1.5\%$, driven by weather-sensitive sectors (construction, trade/transport)
 173 that decline with wetter OND conditions. With more rain, positive responses in cloves and
 174 forestry partially offset these losses, flattening the curve. The nonlinearity stems from the
 175 Gaussian process, and uncertainty widens as we approach the upper limits of our observed
 176 data, where the training data are sparse.

177 Using the posterior elasticity of illegal cases with respect to household earnings (-0.45), the

178 OND rainfall perturbations imply small but systematic changes in illegal resource extraction.
179 A +5 mm OND change in rainfall lowers aggregate OND earnings by $\sim 1\text{--}2\%$ (although this
180 impact is higher if we limit the prediction to solely the OND months), which maps to a $0.5\text{--}1\%$
181 increase in expected illegal cases during OND.) Symmetrically, a 5mm reduction in rainfall
182 raises earnings slightly and predicts a $\sim 2\%$ decrease in illegal cases. Sectoral channels align
183 with the signs of sector-specific elasticities: wetter OND depresses earnings in construction,
184 trade/transport, and manufacturing, pushing up cases of illegal extraction, while gains in
185 cloves (and to a lesser extent forestry) offset part of this rise at larger wet shifts.

186 Finally, before leaving the counterfactual analysis, it is important to note that the non-linear
187 structure of our findings implies that any process—whether weather-related or not—that
188 increases seasonal variability in earnings while holding mean earnings constant can generate
189 large changes in illegal resource extraction. For example, if seasonal earnings were amplified
190 from a typical range of roughly USD 60–140 to a more extreme range of USD 20–180, the
191 predicted annual number of illegal incidents would rise by approximately 20%, increasing from
192 about 56 to roughly 70 cases per year. The intensity of the effect becomes stronger the closer
193 as the low earning parts of the year approaches zero.

194 Discussion

195 We show that: (1) seasonal fluctuations in economy-wide earnings generate systematic vari-
196 ation in illegal resource extraction on Pemba, with higher earnings reducing illegal resource
197 extraction; (2) manufacturing, trade and transport, cloves, and fisheries explain most of these
198 dynamics; and (3) projected increases in OND rainfall modestly depress earnings and therefore
199 raise projected illegal resource extraction.

200 Seasonal income cycles create predictable troughs and peaks in illegal resource extraction
201 consistent with the role of opportunity costs and liquidity constraints in economic models of
202 other crimes. In Becker [1] and Ehrlich [43], individuals weigh the expected returns to legal
203 and illegal activities; when legitimate earnings rise, the relative payoff to illegal extraction
204 falls. Empirical evidence shows similar mechanisms in both urban crime and natural resource
205 settings where income volatility and credit constraints heighten responsiveness to shocks [44,
206 45]. Pemba exhibits these conditions acutely: most labor is informal, and access to credit is
207 minimal, so short-term earnings changes are passed rapidly into illegal extraction behavior.

208 Manufacturing, trade and transport, cloves, services, and fisheries constitute the island’s
209 main cash-generating sectors, and their seasonal earnings cycles determine liquidity condi-
210 tions. Because households are liquidity constrained and rely heavily on purchased food [46],
211 declines in cash flow directly reduce consumption capacity. Two channels link income down-
212 turns to illegal resource extraction: lower opportunity costs of time and tighter liquidity
213 constraints that raise the marginal value of short-term cash. As a small, rural, and rela-
214 tively isolated island, Pemba’s semi-bounded economy makes these sectoral linkages unusually
215 transparent: liquidity generated in cloves and fisheries flows immediately into manufacturing,
216 transport, and services, and contractions induce corresponding reductions in labor demand
217 and earnings. These mechanisms are common to many cash-constrained, resource-dependent
218 economies but are particularly marked in the system we study here, making it a valuable case
219 for the development of general theory.

220 Climate variability interacts with these seasonal mechanisms. Simulations of OND rain-
221 fall—the primary projected climatic anomaly in East Africa [41]—show that wetter OND
222 seasons modestly reduce earnings across key sectors, which in turn modestly increase illegal
223 extraction. These results illustrate how climate shocks propagate through income cycles and

224 induce behavioral responses in settings with incomplete markets.

225 **Seasonal Variation in Earnings**

226 **Cloves**

227 Clove earnings vary with weather-sensitive flowering cycles and irregular boom–bust dynamics
228 [47–51]. Because harvesters are paid per kilogram and government prices are fixed, income
229 variation reflects changes in harvest volume. These cycles generate large seasonal swings in
230 cash income that transmit into the broader economy. Projected increases in OND rainfall
231 may affect these cycles, though longer time series are required for precise identification.

232 **Fishing**

233 Fishing generates higher earnings than clove harvesting and employs a larger share of house-
234 holds [52]. Seasonality is driven by wind and wave conditions affecting access to fishing
235 grounds, with incomes falling during rough seas in June–July. Links to timber use create in-
236 direct connections to illegal wood harvesting [40, 53]. Climate-driven changes in wind regimes
237 or rainfall-induced turbidity caused by shift in the OND may alter these returns and could
238 concentrate income among households with improved vessels.

239 **Market-facing sectors**

240 Manufacturing, services, and trade and transport mirror liquidity cycles in cloves and fish-
241 eries. Demand peaks during harvest periods and religious holidays and contracts during lean
242 months. Reduced liquidity and idle labor during downturns lower the opportunity cost of il-
243 legal extraction, increasing the incentive to access forest or marine resources. These channels
244 propagate seasonal earnings shocks beyond primary sectors.

245 **Seasonality, climate change and conservation policy**

246 At the individual level, illegal harvesting is best understood not in moral or normative frame-
247 work, but as a coping strategy adopted when legitimate income sources contract. In the
248 absence of formal insurance, savings, or credit markets, households turn to resource extrac-
249 tion to bridge temporary liquidity shortfalls and maintain consumption. Such behavior reflects
250 adaptation rather than criminal intent—an effort to manage risk under conditions of pervasive
251 economic uncertainty. Yet these coping strategies carry long-term costs, as they erode the
252 natural resource base that supports future livelihoods, reinforcing a cycle of vulnerability and
253 degradation.

254 illegal resource extraction rises as the opportunity cost of time declines, but we emphasize
255 that in informal economies like Pemba’s, illegality often substitutes for missing financial in-
256 struments. Policy responses should therefore focus on providing safer and more sustainable
257 means of income smoothing—through access to short-term credit, savings groups, or seasonal
258 cash transfers—rather than relying solely on enforcement. Complementary investments in
259 livelihood diversification and small-scale climate adaptation can further stabilize incomes and
260 reduce dependence on illegal extraction as a form of economic self-insurance. Moreover, pre-
261 dictable swings in seasonal income can allow for more targeted and efficient investments in
262 enforcement linked to specific times of year where incomes are low.

263 **Generalizability**

264 Our results provide micro-level evidence of how seasonal income volatility in a resource-
265 dependent, informal economy translates into illegal resource extraction, and how this relation-
266 ship can be affected by climate change, thus linking research on criminology, environmental
267 degradation under economic stress, and climate change. The negative correlation between

268 declining wages or formal earnings and rising illegal behaviour is consistent with the “oppor-
269 tunity cost” channel in the economic theory of crime [1, 2, 43, 54, 55], and recent empirical
270 work emphasizes that the relationship between economic shocks and crime is highly nuanced.
271 For example, Ferraz & Soares [56] show that the impact of economic shocks on crime de-
272 pends on whether the shock is legal or illegal, lootable or not, and the institutional context.
273 Similarly, studies of natural-resource shocks document that reductions in land productivity
274 or crop yields are associated with increases in violence or extraction behaviours in rural set-
275 tings (e.g., [57] for Mexico). The forest-livelihoods literature also treats forests as a “safety
276 net” or gap-filling resource when formal income fails [58]. On Pemba, the seasonal and inter-
277 annual fluctuations in the primary cash-generating sector (cloves, fishing) create predictable
278 downstream stress in manufacturing, trade, transport and services—stress that manifests in
279 increased illegal extraction as households respond rationally to declining liquidity and labour
280 opportunities. However, our results highlight an important point: once we quantify the effect
281 of OND anomalies on sectoral earnings, and the resulting effect of changing earnings on illegal
282 resource extraction, the implied impacts—while non-trivial—do not generate runaway ecolog-
283 ical degradation. Instead, they marginally amplify underlying trends rather than initiating
284 qualitatively new dynamics.

285 However, observing these effects systematically—and determining how generalizable the
286 magnitude of these impacts may be—will require studies conducted across a broader range
287 of environments. This, in turn, demands high-resolution economic data that can be linked to
288 equally high-resolution government records on illegal resource extraction and remote-sensed
289 ecological indicators. Only with such integrated data can we develop a clearer understanding
290 of how different economic pathways mediate these relationships in diverse contexts.

291 Nevertheless, by relying on detailed sector- and time-specific mechanisms, our study con-
292 tributes to the development economics literature by showing how seasonal income cycles,
293 rather than permanent shocks, can also trigger environmentally harmful coping strategies.
294 These processes are likely to be important in other low-income, cash-constrained economies
295 with open access commons, limited formal insurance, and strong seasonality.

296 **Limitations**

297 While our analysis uncovers plausible links between seasonal earnings cycles and illegal re-
298 source extraction, several limitations merit caution and suggest avenues for future work.
299 First, while our time series is high resolution, it is short (only four years) - thus our ability
300 to identify climatic effects, longer-term dynamics, structural breaks or the full life-cycle of
301 the “boom-bust” production cycles is limited. However, it should be noted that most of our
302 backcasting is dependent on projecting the observed seasonal signals back into time and then
303 offsetting them based on known weather variables. Second, our data do not fully disentangle
304 the income-smoothing (liquidity) channel from the labour-substitution (opportunity cost)
305 channel: future research could exploit variation in hourly wage rates, time-use, and access
306 to credit to isolate these mechanisms more clearly. Third, we do not have enforcement data
307 and while our identification strategy accounts for this (see), such data would help assuage
308 any lingering concerns. Fourth, while we interpret the observed illegal extraction as a coping
309 strategy, we cannot rule out that some illegal acts may reflect broader structural issues—such
310 as weak governance, social norms or organised criminal activity—which may also vary season-
311 ally. Finally, experiments or quasi-experimental interventions such as seasonal cash transfers
312 or asset upgrading (e.g., modern boat access) could test whether smoothing income truly
313 reduces illegal extraction, thereby moving from correlation to causal policy design. Address-
314 ing these limitations would both strengthen inference and enhance policy relevance in similar
315 settings globally.

316 **Conclusion**

317 Taken together, our results highlight the importance of viewing illegal resource extraction not
 318 as a simple response to aggregate economic shocks but as a predictable outcome of seasonal
 319 and climatic pressures within local economies. When earnings from dominant cash sectors
 320 fluctuate, these shocks through labor markets may propagate into other economic sectors,
 321 leading to increased pressure on common-pool resources. This is particularly likely to be the
 322 case where households have limited liquidity and/or credit access. By linking high-frequency
 323 economic data with climate variability, our analysis provides a mechanistic account of how
 324 environmental and economic cycles interact. Recognizing these linkages is essential for de-
 325 signing conservation and climate adaptation policies that stabilize rural incomes and reduce
 326 incentives for environmentally destructive activity.

327 **Science for Society**

328 **Materials and Methods**

329 Our methodological approach begins with a static theoretical model that links weather and
 330 earnings to illegal resource extraction, which helps to scaffold the development of a dynamic
 331 theoretical model. The dynamic model allows for the generation of synthetic datasets that we
 332 use to test and validate Bayesian statistical models built in STAN, which we use to empirically
 333 estimate the effects of seasonal sectoral variation in income on illegal resource extraction in
 334 Pemba, Tanzania [59].

335 **Static Model**

Figure 3: Directed Acyclic Graph representing our theoretical model of the relationship between environmental variables E , earnings w in economic sectors k , and observed illegal resource extraction y , which is determined by the true rate of illegal resource extraction h' and enforcement effort I .

336 Figure 3 depicts a simplified causal model, represented using a Directed Acyclic Graph
 337 (DAG), that relates weather patterns, earnings across economic sectors, and rates of illegal
 338 resource extraction. This model allows us to identify confounding variables that must be
 339 controlled for to de-bias the causal paths of interest (sectoral incomes on illegal harvesting).
 340 E is a vector of M instantaneous and lagged weather variables, including maximum daily

341 temperature (represented by the average maximum daily temperature for the past two weeks
342 and the median maximum daily temperature for each of the previous two, three, four, five,
343 and six months), median daily wind speed, and rain (represented by six variables, including
344 cumulative rainfall in the previous two weeks and cumulative rainfall for each of the previous
345 two, three, four, five, and six months). These environmental processes have impacts on
346 earnings w from each of the K sectors of the economy via the paths γ_{MK} . Earnings from
347 these economic sectors affect the rate of illegal harvesting activity h' via the paths φ_k (causally
348 explored below). The rate of illegal harvesting is also directly determined by some subset
349 D of the environmental variables E , via the path ζ . We assume these direct environmental
350 effects are instantaneous, without lags. For example, illegal timber harvesting may be directly
351 affected by rainfall because it slows travel or the increases the difficult of extracting timber
352 from the forest, thus having an instantaneous impact that does not likely carry forward in
353 time.

354 The enforcement effort, I , represents an investment in patrolling and monitoring of the
355 resource stock by the government or community organizations. The enforcement effort is
356 critical for two reasons. First, the actual rate of illegal resource extraction is not observed.
357 Instead, we have to rely on reported cases, y , which are jointly directly determined by the
358 actual rate of illegal resource extraction (via path d) and enforcement efforts (via path p),
359 because a person has to be caught by the authorities for it to enter the official records. Second,
360 the unobserved rate of illegal harvesting depends on the expected cost of being punished, which
361 is a function of enforcement effort (path g). Simultaneously, the rate of illegal infractions
362 also determines the effort invested in enforcement. This bidirectional causation is a happy
363 accident of reality as it ensures that the total effect (although not the direct effect) of w on
364 y is identifiable. Nevertheless, caution is necessary: the estimate can be biased if the rate of
365 illegal resource extraction and enforcement effort are not *exactly* simultaneously determined.
366 Statistically, this means that there will be biases in the estimates if there are lag periods in
367 the adjustment of monitoring and patrolling to the rate of illegal resource extraction and vice
368 versa. The amount of bias will depend on both the length of the lag period (how soon after an
369 increase in illicit activity enforcement is increased and vice versa) and the length of the period
370 over which the data is being aggregated (e.g., days, weeks, months). Shorter lag periods and
371 more extended time aggregation periods will produce less biased estimates.

372 **Dynamic Bioeconomic Model**

373 The simplest way to dynamically represent the theoretical architecture specified in the DAG
374 (Figure 3) is a time allocation model with a two-sector economy. Agents must choose how to
375 allocate their labour: either harvesting from a common pool resource, e , or doing any other
376 kind of work, $1 - e$. A simple payoff function (π) could be as follows:

$$\pi = bh + w(1 - e) \tag{1}$$

377 where b is the benefit of that resource (price), w is the opportunity cost of harvesting (wage
378 rate in the other sector), and the agent's harvest, h , is defined as:

$$h = qe^\nu B^\beta \tag{2}$$

379 Here, q is catchability (total factor productivity), ν is the elasticity of labour on production,
380 B is the resource stock, and β is the elasticity of resource stock on production.

381 Now consider a third-party monitoring institution that determines a maximum allowable

382 harvest (MAH) and inspects agents' harvests with probability I . Overharvesting is defined as
 383 $h' = h > MAH$. If an agent is caught with a harvest greater or equal to h' , they are punished
 384 with cost c (paying a fine). Given this institution, we can rewrite equation 3 as:

$$\pi = \begin{cases} bh + w(1 - e), & \text{where } h \leq MAH. \\ bh' + w(1 - e') - Ic, & \text{where } h' > MAH. \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

385 We define e' as the higher effort required to drive the agent's harvest over the MAH, such
 386 that $e' = e + \hat{e}$, where $0 \leq \hat{e} \leq 1$ and $0 \leq e' \leq 1$. In this case, an agent will overharvest when:

$$Ic < b(h' - h) + w(1 - e') \quad (4)$$

387 In other words, the fundamental mechanism driving illegal harvesting is the cost-benefit
 388 calculation comparing the marginal benefit of illegal harvesting to the cost of being caught
 389 and punished. This is simply a restatement of Becker's work on crime [1]. When equation 4
 390 is true, we expect the agent to participate in illegal harvesting. More precisely, the number
 391 of individuals (N) caught (y) will equal $y = IN$. This condition corresponds with the joint
 392 pathway (p, d) in the causal diagram.

393 Given that we have a simple harvesting model with an institutional layer, we can now link
 394 it to seasonal weather patterns. This can be accomplished by assuming that weather impacts
 395 the marginal productivity of labour, land, and/or the wage rate. For simplicity, we focus on
 396 w , the effect of weather on wage rate, because, under perfect market conditions, changes in
 397 price should also account for marginal changes in land and labour productivity:

$$w = \gamma E + \psi + \epsilon \quad (5)$$

398 Here, E is a matrix of M columns and T rows, each column representing a different envi-
 399 ronmental (weather) variable and each row representing an instantiation of that variable (e.g.,
 400 average maximum daily temperature over the past two weeks) at a particular time point t_i
 401 (noting that some of our weather variables are lagged, e.g. cumulative rainfall in the month
 402 two months prior to t_i). Thus, we can define γ as a vector of length M accounting for the
 403 impact of each weather variable on w . In the real-world case of multiple sectors, γ would
 404 be a matrix of shape (M, K) , however in this simplified case where we only consider one
 405 non-harvesting sector is $(M, 1)$. Here, ψ is some base-rate return for the economic sector
 406 that accounts for all other exogenous determinants of the wage rate, and ϵ is some amount of
 407 randomly distributed noise.

408 If b and Ic are held constant, the only parameter determining illegal harvesting (h') is w .
 409 If seasonal weather patterns cause w to fluctuate, then these weather patterns will produce
 410 different levels of illegal resource extraction as a function of their effect on w . Such a dynamic
 411 can be seen in Figure 4, which shows the results of a stochastic simulation of our theoretical
 412 model.

413 Figure 4 shows how seasonal variability in earnings w (potentially due to weather patterns)
 414 impacts the state of the resource and the amount of illegal resource extraction. In the right
 415 panel, where income is much more variable, there are certain times of the year (one cycle in
 416 the graph) where equation 4 is true. When that threshold is crossed, the system shifts back
 417 and forth from conditions where all agents illegally harvest or do not. The model's 'all or
 418 nothing' behaviour is caused by the fact that all agents in the simulation are assumed to be

Figure 4: Simulated predictions of illegal harvesting. The left-hand panel shows an example of the number of reported cases of illegal resource extraction (red) expected when w (black) is fixed at 0.25. Here, after an initial learning period, we see almost no illegal harvesting and well-maintained natural resources (green). The right-hand panel shows the predicted amount of illegal resource extraction when w has a mean of 0.25 but follows a cyclical process. Here, illegal resource extraction is expected whenever equation 4 is true, which occurs when wages are at the low end of their cycle. Parameter settings for these simulations are $q = .0001$, $b = 0.25$, $\nu = 1$, $\beta = 1$, $I = 0.25$, and $N = 150$.

419 homogeneous. In the real world, agents are heterogeneous in the parameters governing their
 420 payoffs and harvesting functions, and thus, we do not expect such a step-function empirically.
 421 Indeed the number of people caught in illegal resource extraction would be better approxi-
 422 mated by $y = IN_{h'}$, where $N_{h'}$ is the number of people in the population whose payoff and
 423 production functions are such that equation 4 is true, thus producing a smoother gradient in
 424 the relation between economic fluctuations and rates of illegal resource extraction.

425 In Figure 4, both panels share the same mean wage w , but in the left panel w is con-
 426 stant while in the right it oscillates sinusoidally due to seasonality. Because resource recovery
 427 follows nonlinear logistic growth, stock depletion during low-wage periods slows regrowth
 428 and prevents a quick rebound. As a result, wage variability can drive the system into a
 429 low-stock, cyclic equilibrium with elevated illegal harvesting. Moreover, the greater the am-
 430 plitude of these wage swings, the more pronounced the illegal resource extraction and resource
 431 degradation—whereas the constant-wage scenario converges on a single, stable higher-stock
 432 equilibrium.

433 **Estimand**

434 Under this framework, our estimands—the targets of inference—are the changes in the number
 435 of illegal cases documented by the Zanzibari Department of Forestry in Pemba during each
 436 two-week interval that can be attributed to (1) changes in total average earnings and (2)
 437 changes in sector-specific earnings over the same period. In the DAG, estimand (1) is the joint
 438 pathway $\mu(\varphi_{1..k}), g, d, p$. Estimand (2) is the same, except we have K different estimands,
 439 one for each sector-specific impact on the amount of illicit activity ($\varphi_{1..k}$). We note, however,
 440 that we cannot estimate the total effects of sector-specific changes in income, due to the
 441 difficulty in causally modelling intersectoral elasticities outside of correlational covariance
 442 matrices (discussed below).

443 Data

444 Economic Data

445 Our economic data come from four years of a longitudinal research project focused on un-
446 derstanding fine-grained temporal variation in income in Pemba, Tanzania. Eight villages
447 participate in the study: four rural villages, two small market towns, and two main market
448 towns. Income-generating activities in this context primarily involve small-scale subsistence
449 production and market activities such as retail, manufacturing, and service sector employ-
450 ment. We have three hundred participants within these eight villages: 60 individuals in each
451 main market town and 30 individuals in the other six. The sample of communities was se-
452 lected to capture the diversity of livelihoods and community size within Pemba and spans the
453 island’s major economic zones.

454 The data collection protocol is based on standards developed by Beegle et al. [60]. Each
455 household is visited once every two weeks. The data collected consists of all household income
456 and subsistence production for that two-week period, including hours worked and payments-
457 in-kind, all gifts given and received, all debts and credits, and all consumption. The same
458 data are collected at each period using digital devices.

459 As we are interested in earnings, we convert all subsistence production into market values.
460 For each two-week period, we tally all production either consumed directly by the household
461 or sold during that interval. Items produced during the period but held onto and sold during
462 other periods are recorded as earnings during the period in which they were sold. We do not
463 include gifts, remittances or income from repaid debts under earnings.

464 To derive sector-specific earnings, we classified jobs and activities into standard economic
465 sectors, with a few modifications to account for the unique features of Pemba’s economy.
466 First, for primary production, we have five types of farming: ground crops, tree crops, seaweed,
467 cloves, and livestock, as well as fisheries and non-timber forest products. Secondary production
468 activities consist of construction (mainly housing) and manufacturing, which includes all craft
469 specializations. Finally, the tertiary or service sector includes salaries for government workers,
470 bulk trade/retail, and general services, such as healthcare, food services, and transportation.
471 Our data collection protocol also asks about timber harvesting, but we drop this sector from
472 the analysis because it is our outcome variable of interest and because, as an illegal resource
473 extraction, it is likely under-reported in our data. Figure 5 illustrates the average income
474 data for each economic sector.

475 Because illegal resource extraction is reported at the island level (see illegal resource extrac-
476 tion Data, below), we aggregate household-level sector earnings over each two-week period to
477 compute island-wide average sectoral earnings per capita, then sum across sectors to obtain
478 average total per-capita earnings. While this aggregation could bias total-earnings estimates
479 if our sample villages were unrepresentative, we rely on our fairly representative sample of vil-
480 lages without applying spatial weights. Moreover, the observed temporal variation in earnings
481 primarily reflects island-wide ecological cycles, such as monsoon-driven shifts in sector pro-
482 ductivity, and thus, while the absolute magnitudes may be incorrect, the seasonal patterning
483 is accurately represented.

Figure 5: Expected daily earnings across economic sectors. Daily earnings are estimated by distributing the reported two-week earnings evenly over the preceding 14 days. An exponential smoothing function with $\alpha = 0.1$ is applied to reduce noise given the limited sample size. Shaded green areas indicate the major 'mwaka' clove harvest; grey areas denote periods of heavy rainfall; and the red area marks the overlap between the 'vuli' clove and rice harvests.

484 Biophysical Data

485 The four biophysical variables used in this analysis are daily spatial median values for the
 486 Micheweni district of Pemba from January 1, 2011, to November 1, 2025, collated from three
 487 distinct sources. Data on wind speed and temperature were obtained from the ERA5 climate
 488 reanalysis product from Copernicus Climate Change Service, which provides hourly estimates
 489 of global climate and weather for the past 80 years [61]. The temperature data we use is the
 490 maximum temperature recorded at two meters (2m) above the surface of the land, sea, or in-
 491 land waters each day. Wind speed values were produced by taking the square root of the sum
 492 of the squared daily median value for northerly and easterly wind speed. Daily precipitation
 493 data were obtained from the CHIRPS integrated rain gauge and satellite observation inter-
 494 polation product [62]. We use the total recorded rainfall for each day. Finally, wave height
 495 data is the median estimated significant wave height from the WAVEWATCH III model of
 496 the National Weather Service and the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration of
 497 the United States [63]. Significant wave height is defined as the mean wave height of waves
 498 in the highest third of all observations [64].

499 To aggregate the biophysical data to the two-week frequency of the economic data, we
500 used the median of the observed values over each two week period for the daily maximum
501 temperature, daily median wind speed, and daily median wave height. For precipitation, we
502 used the cumulative rainfall over the two-week period.

503 We also generated discrete monthly lagged versions of all the environmental indicators
504 defined above, by recalculating each over the non-overlapping two-, three-, four-, five-, and six-
505 month periods immediately preceding each observation, using the same aggregation methods
506 described above.

Figure 6: Timeseries showing the biophysical data used in this analysis. All data are for the Micheweni district of Pemba from January 1, 2011 to November 1, 2025. Top left: Daily wind speed, represented by the value of the square root of the summed squared daily median northerly and easterly wind speeds. Top right: Total precipitation recorded each day. Bottom left: Daily median significant wave height. Bottom right panel: Maximum daily temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) at 2m above the surface.

507 **Illegal Resource Extraction Data**

508 Data on illegal resource extraction were provided to us by the Department of Forestry from
509 Pemba, Tanzania. Their log books contain all instances of an individual or group being caught
510 and processed by Department of Forestry officials between January 2011 and November 2025.
511 The Department of Forestry has two primary patrol arms, one dedicated to the Ngezi forest
512 reserve in the North and another dealing with the rest of the island. The Ngezi wing is rela-
513 tively well-staffed, while the rest of the island is comparably understaffed. The department’s
514 ability to patrol is often limited by a lack of funds for gasoline. As a result, much of the infor-
515 mation regarding illegal forestry activity across the island reaches the Department of Forestry
516 via concerned citizens or authorities who alert the department to illicit goings-on. Given the
517 potential danger of intervention, the staff at the Department of Forestry first ensure that they
518 have an adequate number of officers and the necessary gas budget before responding to a call.
519 The raw data is seen in the top right panel of Figure ???. Whenever a group of individuals
520 were caught collectively engaging in illicit activity, we treated this as a single event rather
521 than multiple events.

522 Statistical analysis

523 We first outline our general statistical method before explaining the exact functional forms
524 and likelihoods. In short, our modeling approach is comprised of three interrelated estimation
525 procedures that are estimated simultaneously within STAN [59].

526 First, we partition each year into 26 two-week intervals (14 or 15 days) aligned on the same
527 calendar dates across years. Using data from 2022–2026, we then estimate, for each interval,
528 the relationship between sector-specific earnings and a set of predictors: instantaneous and
529 lagged weather variables, Ramadan timing, a periodic term (to capture any remaining seasonal
530 variation), and sectoral economic indicators (see section *Estimating the Effect of Weather on*
531 *Earnings*). Next, leveraging the full time series of daily weather data and known Ramadan
532 dates for Pemba, we apply those parameter estimates to impute sectoral earnings from start
533 of 2011 (see section *Backcasting Earnings*). This procedure relies heavily on the periodic
534 term to capture cyclical patterns, while adjusting for inter annual variation by scaling by
535 the Zanzibari GDP. Finally, with this imputed earnings dataset spanning 2011–2026, we
536 estimate the causal impact of sector-specific household earnings on the island-wide frequency
537 of reported cases of illegal timber harvesting (section *Estimating the Effect of Earnings on*
538 *illegal resource extraction*).

539 The complexity of the statistical procedure arises because our data on illegal harvesting
540 spans 15 years (2011–2026), but our high-resolution economic data spans only four years
541 (2022–2026). Official economic statistics from the Tanzanian government are not available
542 at a sufficiently fine-grained temporal or spatial resolution to adequately capture seasonal
543 variation in earnings. Consequently, we first impute the missing economic data from 2011–
544 2022 and then use this imputed data in the final estimation procedure so that we can leverage
545 the complete dataset on illegal harvesting.

546 A key advantage of our Bayesian framework is that we are able to propagate the uncertainty
547 from all stages of the modelling procedure—including the back-casting of the economic data—
548 through to the final posterior estimates. This allows us to use a smaller fine-grained dataset
549 to draw inferences about longer-term patterns while allowing the uncertainty in the small
550 dataset to be reflected in the posterior estimates.

551 We report all estimated effects and conditional expectations of illegal harvesting as the
552 median estimate and the associated 95% Highest Posterior Density Interval (HPDI). We
553 consider any effect in which the 95% HPDI is entirely positive or negative to have a credible
554 effect on illegal harvesting.

555 Estimating the Effect of Weather on Earnings

556 We begin by investigating the relationship between weather patterns, E_{mt} , and sector-specific
557 earnings, W_{kt} , from 2022 to 2026. We use the additional index t to reflect that these effects
558 are estimated separately for each fixed 14–15 day time period. The following model outlines
559 this relationship:

$$\begin{aligned} W_{kt} &\sim \text{Gamma}(\alpha_{kt}, \phi_k) \\ \alpha_{kt} &= \text{softplus}(\mu_{kt} \cdot \phi_k, 1) \\ \mu_{kt} &= a_k + f_{1k}(P_t) + f_{2k}(E_{mt}, P_t) + \beta_{1k}R_t + \beta_{2k}S_t \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

560 Using the gamma likelihood, with shape parameter α_{kt} and scale parameter ϕ_k , ensures
561 that the imputation procedure produces estimates of the mean on the correct scale based on

562 the linear predictor, μ_{kt} . We use the soft-plus link function introduced by Wiemann et al.
 563 [65], $\text{softplus}(x, \omega) = \frac{\log(1 + \exp(\omega x))}{\omega}$, for all positively constrained variables, using $\omega = 1$. The
 564 softplus function is preferred over the more traditional log link function because of its ability
 565 to avoid numerical overflow through a pseudo-linearization of x .

566 Following the adjustment set required to estimate the total effect of w (earnings) on y (ob-
 567 served illegal forestry activity) based on our DAG [66], we include the following five covariates
 568 for μ_{kt} . First, a_k is the sector-specific intercept. Second, a sector-specific periodic Gaussian
 569 process, f_1 , accounts for any unobserved seasonal variance. Third, a multi-level squared ex-
 570 ponential Gaussian process, f_2 , models the effect of weather (instantaneous and lagged) on
 571 each sector with a flexible non-linear function (see below). Fourth, β_{1k} captures the effect
 572 of Ramadan on sector-specific earnings. Finally, β_{2k} adjusts for the survey version. The β_{2k}
 573 term is necessary because our longitudinal research occasionally involves survey updates to
 574 improve data quality. It corrects for differences in observed earnings estimates due to the
 575 survey version.

576 The multi-level squared-exponential Gaussian process f_2 captures the effects of each weather
 577 variable (and its lags) by modelling deviations rather than raw values: its inputs are the dif-
 578 ferences between each two-week observation and that period’s 13-year average. Additionally,
 579 we denote f_2 with the index k to mark that there is a separate function for each weather
 580 variable (instantaneous and lagged measures for all four weather processes) in each economic
 581 sector. In this way, the Gaussian process allows each period to have its own specific non-linear
 582 effect linking changes in weather patterns to changes in sector-specific earnings, without im-
 583 posing a specific functional form. We use partial-pooling to account for covariance between
 584 the effects of variables across time-periods. To do this, we relate the period-specific effects
 585 (Z_{pmk}) through a hyperparameter σ_{mk} and add this to the mean effect of the variable δ_{mk} :

$$f_{2k} = \sum_{m=1}^M L_{mk}(Z_{pmk}\sigma_{mk} + \delta_{mk}) \quad (7)$$

$$f_{\text{exp}^2}(D, \eta, \rho, \sigma_{\text{exp}^2}) = L_{mk}L_{mk}^H$$

586 L_{mk} represents the covariance matrix of different values of the environmental variable on
 587 sector-specific earnings. We use a non-centered definition of the Gaussian process, where
 588 partial pooling occurs on the offsets. The lower triangle of the covariance matrix L_{mk} is
 589 constructed by taking the Cholesky decomposition of the output of a squared exponential
 590 kernel (f_{exp^2}), where L_{mk}^H is the transposed, complex conjugate of L_{mk} . This partial pooling
 591 also helps deal with the relatively low number of observations per period.

592 Backcasting Earnings

593 After estimating the relationship between weather and sectoral earnings from March 2022
 594 to November 2025, we impute W_{kt} for all earlier periods. To do so, we compile historical
 595 Ramadan dates and daily weather records dating back to January 1, 2011, and substitute them
 596 (together with the periodic term) into equation 6 to generate sectoral earnings estimates. We
 597 omit the survey version offsets β_{2k} so that each imputed value reflects marginalized earnings
 598 averaged across all survey waves.

599 Finally, we account for measurement error in our observed earnings data by introducing
 600 random measurement error following the methodology outlined by McElreath [67]:

$$\begin{aligned}
W_{kt,\text{true}} &\sim \text{Gamma}(W_{kt,\text{error}} \cdot \epsilon, \epsilon) \\
\epsilon &= \sqrt{\frac{W_{kt,\text{obs}} \cdot 0.1}{W_{kt,\text{obs}}}} \\
W_{kt,\text{error}} &= \text{softplus}((W_{kt,\text{obs}} - \beta_{2k}S_t), 1)
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Using ϵ , we impose rather conservative estimates on the amount of measurement error, aiming for a variance of 10% of the observed value for any given time point ($W_{kt,\text{obs}}$). The calculation for ϵ is derived from an algebraic rearrangement of the variance of a Gamma distribution and ensures that, regardless of the scale of the observed data, the amount of measurement error always approximates 10%. Without more effective ways to know exactly how much measurement error is included in our data, the choice of this value is arbitrary.

We then combine the imputed values of W_{kt} (before March 2022) with the error-adjusted W_{kt} (after March 2022) to obtain complete estimates of sector-specific earnings for all time points for which we have data on illegal resource extraction.

Estimating the Effect of Earnings on Illegal Resource Extraction

With the expected sectoral earnings for each time point, we then estimate the causal impact of earnings on the number of documented cases of illegal harvesting, y_t . While it would seem natural to estimate the causal impact using a negative binomial, the non-collapsibility of even a pseudo-linear link function means that parameters have no causal interpretation unless fully linearized. Thus, $y'_t = \frac{(y_t - \bar{y}_t)}{\sigma_y}$ is just standardized y_t .

$$\begin{aligned}
y'_t &\sim \text{N}(\mu_t, \sigma) \\
\mu_t &= a_y + \sum_{k=1}^K \beta_{3k} \log(W_{kt}) + \sum_{d=1}^D f_3(E_{dt}) + f_4(Z_t) + f_5(P_t) + \beta_4 R + \beta_5 T
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

A time-invariant intercept, denoted as a_y , serves as the baseline expectation for the number of reported cases. To capture the impact of (logged) sectoral earnings W_{kt} , we have a random effect slope $\beta_{3k} = b_{3k}\sigma_3 + \bar{b}_3$ for each sector. To capture the direct effect of biophysical drivers D , such as total precipitation and median temperature, on the amount of illegal resource extraction, we define a vector of Gaussian processes with squared exponential kernels, $f_3(E_{dt})$.

To account for annual and seasonal trends, we use a squared exponential Gaussian process and a periodic Gaussian process, respectively. The squared exponential Gaussian process, denoted as $f_4(Z_t)$, models the year-on-year effect. The periodic Gaussian process, denoted as $f_5(P_t)$, captures any periodic trend not captured by seasonal economic fluctuations, direct environmental effects, timber prices, or Ramadan. The indicator variable, β_4 , represents a fixed effect for whether at least one day of the period falls within the holy month of Ramadan. This variable allows us to assess whether Ramadan has a distinct impact on reported illegal activities. Finally, to account for the effect of the changing value of timber and forest resources, we include a term β_5 , which accounts for the lagged world timber price T .

Elasticity estimation. To quantify the marginal effect of household earnings on illegal resource extraction, we derive the elasticity of illegal cases with respect to income from the posterior distribution of model parameters. Because the model employs a softplus link, the

634 elasticity cannot be read directly from the regression coefficient on log earnings. Instead, we
 635 linearize the link function around the posterior mean of the latent predictor, holding all other
 636 parameters at their expected values. Specifically, we compute the expected earnings level \bar{W}
 637 and its softplus-transformed derivative to obtain a scaling factor

$$\kappa_{\text{ref}} = \bar{C} \cdot \frac{\sigma(\eta_{\text{ref}})}{\text{softplus}(\eta_{\text{ref}})},$$

638 where $\sigma(\cdot)$ is the logistic function and η_{ref} is the reference linear predictor. The posterior
 639 elasticity is then defined as

$$\varepsilon = \kappa_{\text{ref}} \mu_{\text{gdp}},$$

640 where μ_{gdp} denotes the posterior draws of the coefficient linking aggregate earnings to illegal
 641 cases. This transformation rescales the coefficient onto the elasticity scale, ensuring compa-
 642 rability with models using log links while retaining the stability of the softplus formulation.
 643 The resulting posterior distribution of ε provides an interpretable measure of the proportional
 644 change in illegal cases for a proportional change in household earnings.

645 **Forecasting under OND rainfall perturbations.** To assess how future changes in
 646 the OND rainfall season may influence illegal resource extraction, we simulate counterfac-
 647 tual shifts in OND precipitation by perturbing the environmental predictors that enter the
 648 Gaussian-process imputation of sectoral earnings. Specifically, we adjust the rain and lagged
 649 rain indices for all OND periods by increments of $\pm 5\text{--}15$ mm month⁻¹, while holding all other
 650 environmental and temporal predictors at their posterior means. For each perturbed scenario,
 651 we propagate the modified inputs through the fitted Gaussian processes to obtain new poste-
 652 rior predictions of sectoral earnings, aggregate them to household income, and finally translate
 653 the resulting changes in earnings into predicted changes in illegal cases using the posterior
 654 elasticity ε . This approach isolates the economic consequences of OND rainfall anomalies
 655 and quantifies their indirect effects on illegal resource extraction through income-mediated
 656 channels.

657 Model Validation

658 One benefit of our dynamic simulation is its ability to generate synthetic data for validating
 659 statistical models. Our validation process involves two stages. First, we simulate the effect
 660 of weather on earnings and assess whether our statistical models can accurately learn these
 661 relationships, even when only a few years of economic data are available to pair with weather
 662 data. Second, we simulate the effect of seasonal economic earnings on illegal resource extrac-
 663 tion and test whether the model can recover the true impact of earnings on illegal behavior,
 664 even when relying heavily on imputed data.

665 The first step in validation is to ensure that our model can learn the impact of weather on
 666 earnings across different sectors. To generate synthetic datasets, we create a set of M ($M = 2$)
 667 weather variables with distinct seasonal trends, and K ($K = 3$) sectors, including one “illegal”
 668 sector, and relate the weather variables to the wage rate in each sector via Equation 5. Then,
 669 using our theoretical model, we simulate synthetic datasets, sweeping across different values
 670 of γ (0.01–0.2) and ϵ (0.01–0.2). Other parameters are set as follows: $b = 2$, $B = 25000$,
 671 $q = 0.0001$, $\alpha = \beta = 1$, $I = 0$, $c = 0$, $N = 150$, $T = 2000$.

672 To evaluate model performance, we assess prediction accuracy—specifically, how well the
 673 model predicts earnings when estimating the impact of weather using only four years of
 674 data. We construct a counterfactual dataset by iteratively running the generative model and
 675 evaluating the statistical model’s performance on estimating earnings while systematically
 676 varying the parameters γ (the effect of weather on earnings) and ϵ (random noise). This

Figure 7: Model performance in predicting the economic impacts of climate change in simulated datasets. Along the y-axis, we increase $\gamma_{1,1}$, the impact of the first weather process on the first economic sector. Along the x-axis, we increase the ϵ , the amount of noise in the relationship between weather and wages, where $\epsilon \sim N(0, \epsilon)$. The color of each cell indicates the model prediction error normalized by the magnitude of earnings in the section such that the predicted error is equal to $(\pi_{obs} - \pi_{est})/\pi_{obs}$.

677 allows us to determine how large the effect size must be, relative to the noise, to estimate
 678 earnings accurately. Our performance metric, predicted error, measures the difference between
 679 the estimated and actual parameter values, expressed as a percentage of the true value.

680 Figure 7 illustrates the model’s performance in predicting earnings. Overall, model per-
 681 formance declines as both the level of noise and the impact of weather on earnings increase,
 682 although the effect is more pronounced for the noise parameter. As the number of years in-
 683 creases, the model’s ability to learn γ improves. However, given the data constraints we face,
 684 performance remains limited when the relationship between weather and earnings is strong.
 685 Notably, prediction error remains below 5% as long as $\gamma < 0.15$. Since the relationship be-
 686 tween weather and earnings is difficult to estimate with only four years of data, we treat this
 687 component primarily as a marginal improvement to the imputation process. Most seasonal
 688 variation is captured by the periodic terms, with weather variables providing only modest
 689 additional value.

690 The second part of our model validation procedure tests whether the model can accurately
 691 recover the relationship between illegal harvesting and earnings, even when a large portion
 692 of the earnings data must be imputed. As in the previous step, we use a generative model,
 693 where agents update their effort allocations adaptively through payoff-biased social learning.
 694 Specifically, agents adjust their behavior each period based on the payoffs observed in the
 695 same season of the previous year (e.g., decisions for the current spring are based on payoffs
 696 from the prior spring).

697 We run this model for 2,000 years to allow the system to reach equilibrium. From the
 698 full simulation, we extract the final 14 years of data and estimate the relationship between
 699 sector-specific earnings and the rate of illegal harvesting. We then reduce the earnings dataset
 700 to only the final four years and impute the earnings data for the preceding 10 years using
 701 the statistical model described earlier. This setup allows us to evaluate the conditions under
 702 which the true parameter values can still be recovered despite extensive imputation. We
 703 conduct parameter sweeps over two key variables: b , the benefit of harvesting the natural
 704 resource (adjusting for wage opportunity costs), and I , the probability of inspection.

705 The results in Figure 8A show the posterior contrast, meaning the absolute difference be-

Figure 8: Model performance in predicting earnings on the number of cases. Panel A shows sweeps along b on the x-axis and I along the y-axis, with the colour gradient showing the mean contrast $(\beta_{3,true} - \beta_{3,imp})/\beta_{3,true}$. Panel B shows the same sweeps but with the gradient representing the absolute size of v .

706 tween the model estimates of the predicted number of cases in the “true” data and in the
 707 imputed data. The vast majority of simulations exhibit minimal differences between the con-
 708 ditions where the statistical model sees the complete data and where imputation is used.
 709 Outside the pink regions, the contrast estimates are below 1 and the mean effect size (Figure
 710 8B) is approximately -10 . In these cases, the mean estimated difference is below 10%.

711 However, certain parameter combinations sharply decrease model performance. This is
 712 particularly true when both the inspection probability (I) and the benefit (b) of harvesting
 713 are relatively large. Specifically, the pink section in Figure 8A indicates a region where the
 714 benefits from harvesting are substantial, but the cost of being caught overharvesting is also
 715 very high. In this area, the amount of overharvesting is highly susceptible to fluctuations in
 716 relative prices (the ratio of b to w) and becomes highly dependent on stochastic events, making
 717 the true effect difficult to observe over short time periods. When the inspection probability
 718 becomes very high, it will drive almost all overharvesting from the population.

719 A very high variance in the number of cases reported seasonally, no variance in y , or a
 720 highly zero-inflated distribution in y can be used as indicators of whether the aforementioned
 721 conditions are likely to result in poor model performance in the real dataset. These are not
 722 characteristics of our dataset. On Pemba, illegal forestry activity occurs regularly, and the
 723 inspection probability is low. Consequently, we expect the model to be able to approximate
 724 the true parameter values in our dataset.

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727 End Matter

728 During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT in order to proofread pre-
 729 written text. After using this service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed
 730 and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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